

Exploiting Forecasting for Automatic Network Service Operations in Digital Twin Applications

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Abstract—This demo highlights and experimentally proves the adoption of the Forecasting Functional Block (5Gr-FFB) in the orchestration and monitoring operations of the 5G Network Services (NS). In particular, the demo will show how to instantiate an NS with related monitoring functionalities and exploit the 5Gr-FFB for generating forecasting metrics. The interactions among 5Gr-FFB and the other orchestration functional blocks (i.e., the Service Orchestrator (5Gr-SO) and the Vertical oriented Monitoring System (5Gr-VoMS)) will be highlighted. The demo considers a robotic Digital Twin use-case deployed at 5Tonic premises. This work represents a first step towards the evolution of advanced close loop operations, consuming hybrid metrics (i.e., retrieved from the monitoring components and the forecasting ones) to perform automatic NS operations with margin in time.

Index Terms—Digital twin, forecasting, 5G platform, automatic service scaling

I. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine learning (ML) in Network Service Control, Orchestration, and Management is becoming a powerful and promising technique to enable zero touch network and service management [1].

On top of the developed 5Growth platform [2], which is used to deploy and manage requested network services and slices over a shared 5G infrastructure, the AIML procedures were introduced into the development of new functional blocks to efficiently handle and guarantee the Service Level Agreement (SLA), by enabling automatic scaling operations.

The novel 5Gr-Forecasting Functional Block (5Gr-FFB) has been integrated into the 5G service management platform [3] developed in the 5Growth project to compute forecasting metrics on demand. More specifically, scaling operations at the Service Orchestrator (5Gr-SO) can rely on forecasting values to react to future events with a time margin and hence avoiding/limiting the SLA violation. In case of forecasting procedure, the interaction with the 5Gr-FFB is exploited. The selected forecasting model consumes real-time data (as input features) producing the forecast version of the metric, being integrated with the monitoring platform as a regular probe.

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Finally, the forecasting data can be consumed at the service orchestration layer to make decisions regarding the network service scaling operations to be applied in the 5Growth stack.

This demo is an evolution of the previously proposed design and validation of the AI/ML platform. In this demo, we focus on the 5Gr-FFB module, highlighting the internal workflow and its integration with the 5Gr architecture. The integration is validated considering a robotic Digital Twin use-case in the context of Industry 4.0 as a reference Network service (NS).

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND WORKFLOW

Fig. 1a shows the high level view of the orchestration stack designed and developed in the 5Growth project. In the rest of this section, the main functional blocks with related functionalities are described.

The *Vertical Slicer (5Gr-VS)* is the common entry point for all verticals to submit the requests of vertical services. It processes the vertical service requests, mapping them to network slices for deployment.

The *Service Orchestrator (5Gr-SO)* is the component devoted to the network service and resource orchestration. It performs the end-to-end orchestration of NFV-Network Services (NFV-NS), based on service requirements and availability of the services/resources. In addition it is responsible for the management of their lifecycles (including on-boarding, instantiation, update, scaling, termination).

The *Vertical-oriented Monitoring System (5Gr-VoMS)* constitutes the monitoring platform for heterogeneous services, network and technological domains. It offers specific functionalities, including data distribution and dynamic probe (re)configuration. The platform also exposes a GUI for real time monitoring of specific API, with dashboards created and maintained during the network service evolution.

The *AI/ML Platform (5Gr-AIMLP)* is the functional block in charge of onboarding, training and managing AI models, by relying on the monitoring data collected by the 5Gr-VoMS. It exposes a catalogue of the available AI models, able to tune/chain them for the generation of more complex models. The 5Gr-AIMLP is typically triggered by the 5Gr-SO, being able to retrieve on demand context information and

Fig. 1. a) High-level 5Growth orchestration architecture; b) Digital Twin network service overview.

performance metrics to complement its available datasets in order to update a model or compute its reward.

The *Forecasting Functional Block (5Gr-FFB)* is a novel block, with respect to the original architecture, that aims at generating forecast values of parameters monitored by the 5Gr-VoMS. The 5Gr-FFB is configured by the 5Gr-SO, receiving all the input parameters required to: (i) select the proper model to be executed, (ii) interact with the 5Gr-VoMS to receive all required parameters (input of the forecasting model) and (iii) expose the data, behaving like a regular probe, to be collected by the 5Gr-VoMS. In this way the 5Gr-FFB, starting from the retrieved metrics data (including the metric to be forecast), exposes forecast data to the decisional elements, such as the 5Gr-SO, to take a proactive approach in reacting to change NS state (i.e., scaling in/out a NS instance or scaling up/down resources to meet SLA requirements).

III. DEMO WORKFLOW

Fig. 1b shows the considered robotic Digital Twin (DT) Network service graph. Four VNFs, running in separate VMs, are connected to control connected robots: VNF1 performs the robot control (and it is the most time crucial VNF); VNF2 is responsible for the motion planning; VNF3 performs the interface management, while VNF4 is responsible for the DT App. The incoming of a new robot triggers the activation of a new docker container instance for each VNF.

During the demo the key functionalities of the 5Growth orchestration platform will be showcased and validated, with particular focus on the operations related to 5Gr-FFB.

- 1) The 5Gr-SO performs the Network Service instantiation:
 - it instantiates the DT Network service, including the four VNFs and the related networking connectivity;
 - it triggers the 5Gr-VoMS to activate the monitoring probes listed in the Network Service Descriptor (NSD), i.e., the round trip time (RTT) latency of the robots at the application level and the VNF1 CPU occupancy;
- 2) The 5Gr-VoMS configures monitoring jobs:
 - Activates and configures all the required probes;
 - Creates the GUI dashboards in Grafana to show the considered metrics;

- Starts the Prometheus jobs to collect all the data from the probes with proper frequency.
- 3) The 5Gr-SO activates the 5Gr-FFB via a REST API, providing the parameters to complete all the actions (i.e., NS ID, VNF ID, NS type, the metric to be forecast, the instantiation Level)
 - 4) The 5Gr-FFB performs forecasting jobs:
 - Uses VNF ID, NS type and the metric to select the model (i.e., Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM));
 - Activates the required scraped jobs, to retrieve all the required data (i.e., input features of the model)
 - After the activation of the forecasting job, starts a Prometheus job to collect forecasting data.

IV. INNOVATION AND RELEVANCE

In this demo, the 5Gr-FFB functional module will be presented to compute the forecasting of the key metrics related to a Network Service. The 5Gr-FFB has been successfully integrated with the 5Growth orchestration stack to assist automated zero-touch network service management.

The behaviour of the 5Gr-FFB has been validated in a Digital Twin use-case. The functional block is capable of forecasting a key metric, correlating multiple input features collected by the monitoring platform. The design of the integrated system allows to transparently adopt real data and/or forecast data for making smarter decisions to perform automatic service operations for different application use cases (i.e., automated VNF scaling).

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